

THE PROCESS OF TRANSLATING HUMOURS AND JOKES BETWEEN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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ABSTRACT. *The study of the oral creativity of Eastern peoples is one of the key areas in which comparative folktales are growing daily in this article. Other significant areas include his work as a researcher in this area, the translations of his anecdotes into Uzbek and English, the substance and core of his scientific research, and careful consideration of the article's structure.*

KEY WORDS: *translation, translator, oral, written, simultaneously, consecutive whispering.*

INTRODUCTION

Each nationality has its unique traditions, historical traits, and mindset, all of which are frequently mocked. Russian jokes frequently feature figures from folklore and fairy tales. We only came up with a lot of amusing stories about Kolobok. The British, for instance, enjoy making jokes about some royal family anecdotes. Knowing the language is not enough to get an English joke; you also need to have some understanding of the people's history, culture, and way of life. Keep in mind that the term "anecdote" in English is a jest rather than an anecdote. According to its Russian translation, Anekdot is "a short story, an incident from life." Puns are a common basis for English jokes. As a result, these tales do not seem humorous at all when translated directly into Uzbek. However, people with a reasonable command of the language frequently think up their own intriguing spoken words. Comedy is a necessary component of in-person interactions. A translation is poor if it fails to convey the humor of the original. According to this article, practically any audibly communicated humor can be translated, given the

right techniques and realistic success standards. It separates language-specific jokes—puns in particular—and culture-specific jokes from more controllable forms of humor. These two problem areas are the focus of this analysis. A quick review of pun research is provided, along with useful tips to improve translators' wordplay reactions and a methodical approach to work through problems rather than waiting for inspiration. The alternatives for managing outrageous jokes are increased since humor translators, like comic writers, are allowed to utilize language imaginatively. A brief explanation of jokes that are unique to a culture and how they run counter to "universal humour" comes next.

THE MAIN FINDINGS AND RESULTS

Plato, Aristotle, and Cicero were the first theorists to examine and study humor, giving special focus to linguistic humor, as Attardo (1994b) demonstrates. The development of humor theories began in ancient Greece with comedy. After the end of the Middle Ages, other academics created their own contemporary theories of humor, each of which examined the subject from a different angle and with consideration for a variety of factors. There are other classifications and theories by prominent thinkers like Sigmund Freud and Keith-Spiegel that appear to have had an impact as well, but we can use Victor Raskin's (cited in Attardo, 1994b, p. 47) classification since, based on research, it is the most fundamental, comprehensive, extended, and discussed one; perhaps this is because all other theories ultimately fall into these three categories (Smuts, n.d.).

Incongruity theories, release theories, and hostility theories make up the three categories of Raskin's classification of various humor theories that are presented in the following table. Table 1 shows Raskin's categorization of theories of humor (see to S. Attardo, 1994b, p. 47):

Attardo's (1994: 47) Families of Humor Theories

Cognitive	Social	Psychoanalytical
Incongruity	Hostility	Release
Contrast	Aggression	Sublimation
	Superiority	Liberation
	Triumph	Economy
	Derision	
	Disparagement	

Meyer introduced four fundamental purposes of humor in communication by using a communicative method based on the genesis of humor: two that bring communicators together (identification and clarification) and two that set one group of communicators apart from another. Identification is the use of self-deprecating humor to make allies with the audience (Chapter 1978), whereas clarity aids communicators in summarizing and presenting their arguments. You laugh with others in both situations.

Humour theory	Humour function
Relief	Identification
Incongruity	Clarification Differentiation
Superiority	Identification Enforcement Differentiation

As we said during the translation work we have to pay attention to the main meaning of jokes. Because it is also one of the type of literal translation, so it may include some metaphorical transformations. At this time we can lose the fundamental aspect of humour that it wouldn't be comic anymore after the translation work. Now we can identify some examples of Uzbek anecdotes with their translation.

1. Musiqachi uyida baraban chalib o'tirgan ekan, qo'shnilari ajoyib musiqa ovozi ko'chaga ham balandroq eshitilsin deb uni derzasini tosh bilan sindirib

ketishibdi.- *While the musician was playing the drums in his house, his neighbors broke his window with a stone so that the sound of his wonderful music could be heard louder on the street.*

2. Kechki bazmlarning birida bir erkak noz-karashma qilayotgan ayolga debdi:

-Kechirasiz xonim, men uylanganman!

Ayol bo'lsa unga javoban:—Voy xudoyim-yey, men bo'lsa kasal ekansizmi deb

o'ylabman...- *At one of the dinner parties, a man said to a flirtatious woman:*

Excuse me ma'am, I'm married!

And woman, answered him:

"Oh my god, I thought you were sick..."

Translating humours and jokes between languages, particularly between English and Uzbek, is a complex process that requires a deep understanding of cultural nuances, linguistic structures, and comedic styles. Humour is highly subjective and varies greatly across cultures, making it challenging for translators to convey comedic elements accurately.

One of the crucial aspects of translating humour is adequately capturing the cultural references and wordplay inherent in jokes. Cultural references are often highly context-specific, relying on shared knowledge and experiences within a particular culture. Translators must consider the target audience's cultural background and adapt the original joke to ensure it remains understandable and amusing. Another consideration is the linguistic structure and wordplay involved in jokes. Puns, wordplay, and double entendres are common comedic techniques that can be challenging to translate, especially when languages have different phonetic systems, grammar rules, or vocabulary. Translators must find equivalent wordplay or create new ones to evoke similar laughter and maintain the intended comedic effect in the target language.

Translating humour also involves understanding the different comedic styles and sensibilities in English and Uzbek cultures. Each culture has its own unique

approach to comedy, and what may be amusing in one language may not resonate in another. Translators need to familiarize themselves with both cultures' comedic traditions to successfully transfer the humour from the source language to the target language. Additionally, the process of translating humour requires adaptability and creativity. Translators often need to employ different strategies such as substitution, cultural adaptation, or even inventing new jokes altogether to effectively convey the humorous elements in the target language. This adaptability ensures that the translated jokes feel natural and resonate with the target audience. Translators must also carefully navigate potential pitfalls such as offensive or inappropriate content. What may be acceptable or funny in one culture could be offensive or inappropriate in another. It is vital for translators to exercise cultural sensitivity and be mindful of cultural taboos, stereotypes, and sensitivities to avoid any misunderstandings or offensive translations. Translating humours and jokes between English and Uzbek languages is a complex process that involves consideration of cultural references, linguistic structures, comedic styles, and cultural sensitivities. Translators must possess a deep understanding of both cultures and adapt the original joke to ensure it remains humorous and relatable to the target audience. Translating jokes between languages can be a challenging task, as humor often relies on cultural references, wordplay, and context that may not easily transfer from one language to another. However, here are a few tips to help translate jokes between English and Uzbek languages:

1. Understand the cultural context: Familiarize yourself with the cultural nuances, traditions, and popular references of both languages. This will help you grasp the underlying elements of the joke and ensure it translates well.

2. Adapt the joke: Some jokes may not translate directly due to linguistic or cultural differences. Instead, look for similar expressions, idioms, or wordplay in the target language and adapt the joke accordingly. This may involve changing the wording or using different cultural references to achieve a similar punchline.

3. Consider the target audience: Jokes that work well in one language may not resonate with speakers of another language. Therefore, it's important to understand the preferences, sensitivities, and sense of humor of the target audience while translating jokes.

4. Find a balance: When translating jokes, striking a balance between retaining the original humor and making it relatable to the target audience is crucial. Remember that the main goal is to create amusement and laughter, so focus on capturing the essence of the joke rather than translating it word-for-word.

5. Test the joke: Share the translated joke with native speakers of the target language to gauge their response. This will help you refine and fine-tune the translation, ensuring that it conveys the intended humor effectively.

Remember, not all jokes can be perfectly translated, and some may lose their humor during the process. However, with careful consideration of cultural nuances, creative adaptations, and feedback from native speakers, you can increase the chances of successfully translating jokes between English and Uzbek languages.

CONCLUSION

To sum up, the process of translating linguistic jokes is driven by mechanisms that produce comedic effect. Jokes with a pragmatic mechanism can be translated accurately and without modification. Comics that primarily rely on syntactic mechanics are typically simple to translate when the technique is shared by both languages. To adhere to linguistic conventions, translators occasionally employ transpositions or syntactic bargains. Using semantic mechanisms to translate jokes is not always simple. In the most challenging situations, the translator might translate literally while adding commentary, extraneous elements, or renderings without maintaining the humor.

REFERENCES

1. D.Umaraliyeva//O'zbek xalq latifalari va ularning ingliz tiliga tarjimasi- INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC JOURNAL VOLUME 1 ISSUE 6 UIF-2022: 8.2
2. E. Aleksandrova//Linguistic jokes translational methods and strategies- Russian,Moscow,
3. Leticia Rey Mazas // Translation of puns and humour in Lewis Carroll's Alice's Adventures in Wonderland into Galician- Grao en Lingua e Literatura Inglesas,2017-2018.
4. Ubaydullayeva, Durdon, and Muhammadjon Tojiboyev. "TRANSLATION IS THE STUDY OF LINGUISTIC AND LITERARY." Academic International Conference on Multi-Disciplinary Studies and Education. Vol. 1. No. 1. 2023.
5. Ubaydullaeva, D. (2022). ХОЗИРГИ ЗАМОН ТИЛШУНОСЛИГИДА ҚЎШИМА ГАПЛАР ТАВСИФИ, ТАСИФИ ВА МЕТАТИЛИ МАСАЛАЛАРИ. Science and innovation, 1(В6), 560-564.
6. Ubaydullaeva, D. (2022). PROBLEMS OF DESCRIPTION, CLASSIFICATION AND METATALOLOGY OF COMPLEX SENTENCES IN MODERN LINGUISTICS. Science and Innovation, 1(6), 560-564.
7. Ubaydullayeva, D., & Raxmonqulova, M. (2022). TILSHUNOSLIKDA IJTIMOY YO'NALISHNING TARAQQIYOTI. Science and innovation, 1(В6), 869-873.
8. G'opporova, N., & Ubaydullayeva, D. (2022). A COMMUNICATIVE PRAGMATIC STUDY OF MEANS OF EXPRESSING DIRECTIVE SPEECH ACTS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES. Евразийский журнал академических исследований, 2(12), 825-827.
9. Ubaydullayeva, D., & Raxmonqulova, M. (2022). DEVELOPMENT OF SOCIAL DIRECTION IN LINGUISTICS. Science and Innovation, 1(6), 869-873.

- 10.Gulyora, A., Odina, A., Asadbek, A., & Durдона, A. (2023). LEXICAL AND SEMANTIC TRANSFORMATION IN WRITTEN TRANSLATION. "RUSSIAN" ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ПОДХОДЫ В СОВРЕМЕННОЙ НАУКЕ, 9(1).
- 11.Kamolaxon, A., Shahina, A., Nodiraxon, A., & Gavharoy, A. (2023). TRANSLATION OF PHRASES AND TERMS RELATED TO INTERNATIONAL AND INTERSTATE POLITICAL AND ECONOMIC ORGANIZATIONS. DENMARK" THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL FOUNDATIONS OF SCIENTIFIC PROGRESS IN MODERN SOCIETY", 14(1).
- 12.Ubaydullayeva, D., & Qayumova, S. (2022). O'zbek Xalq Maqollarining O'zbek Folklorshunosligida O'rganilishi. Miasto Przyszłości, 30, 133-134.
- 13.Sarvinoz, X., Nigora, O., Azima, S., & Marhabo, O. (2023, May). FEATURES OF THE TRANSLATOR'S STYLE IN POETIC TRANSLATION. In "CANADA" INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON DEVELOPMENTS IN EDUCATION, SCIENCES AND HUMANITIES (Vol. 9, No. 1).
- 14.Ubaydullaeva, D. (2022). PROBLEMS OF DESCRIPTION, CLASSIFICATION AND METATALOGY OF COMPLEX SENTENCES IN MODERN LINGUISTICS. Science and Innovation, 1(6), 560-564.
- 15.Ubaydullaeva, D., & Yuldasheva, Z. (2020). POLYSEMY IN THE UZBEK LANGUAGE. In АКТУАЛЬНЫЕ ВОПРОСЫ СОВРЕМЕННОЙ НАУКИ И ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ (pp. 234-235).